

1 **State of the evidence on the impacts of fishing plastic waste to**
2 **coastal communities: Protocol for a Systematic Evidence Map**

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13 **Structured abstract**

14 **Background:** Fishing plastic waste (FPW) is known to cause multidimensional impacts to coastal
15 communities globally. Detailed information on the environmental, socioeconomic and technical
16 dimensions of effects to coastal communities caused by FPW has yet to be collated and considered in
17 one place. **Methods:** The main aim of this study is to identify, organise and group existing primary
18 evidence of the environmental, social, economic, political, and technical impacts of FPW on coastal
19 communities and identify gaps in our knowledge about which types of FPW are most problematic.
20 **Search Strategy:** We will search several databases across four electronic academic indexes (Web of
21 Science, Scopus, PubMed and EBSCOhost [Business Source Complete, CINAHL Plus, EconLit,
22 GreenFile, and Humanities International Index]). **Eligibility Criteria:** Eligible studies must contain
23 primary research investigating an environmental, social, economic, political, or technical impact of
24 fragments of any size of plastic polymers (macro-, micro-, or nano-) originating from fishing equipment
25 (i.e., capture and ancillary) that has been abandoned, lost, or otherwise discarded in the marine
26 environment, affecting fishing gear (ALDFG) to any defined human or non-human (vertebrates,
27 invertebrates, micro-organisms) individual, group or assemblage of individuals, relying on coastal and
28 ocean resources. Environmental impacts include physical and physiological effects to biotic and abiotic
29 elements of marine ecosystems. Social impacts include impacts to community health and wellbeing.
30 Economic impacts include impacts to livelihood and trade. Political impacts include responses from

31 local or regional governments to address FPW. Technical impacts include effects to techniques
32 employed by fisherfolk or to the management of FPW at the local level. **Screening & Extraction:** Our
33 search was optimised on Cadima. Articles will be screened at title and abstract, before a full-text review.
34 All articles will be screened by a single reviewer, with two additional reviewers assessing articles for
35 consistency. One out of ten articles will be screened by two additional reviewers in duplicate as a quality
36 control. Data extraction will be performed on all articles included at full text, and articles that do not
37 meet the eligibility criteria will be excluded. All articles excluded at full text will be confirmed by the
38 two additional reviewers. **Study Mapping & Reporting:** Results will be published in a narrative
39 summary and visualised in a publicly available, user-friendly, interactive and interrogable evidence map
40 on Tableau.

41

42 **1. Introduction**

43 **1.1. Background and Rationale**

44 Plastics are synthetic or semi-synthetic organic polymers that have become entrenched in modern-day
45 society due to their beneficial characteristics, such as their affordability, durability, lightweightness,
46 mouldability and insulating capabilities (Derraik, 2002; Thompson *et al.*, 2009). A consequence of these
47 characteristics is that plastics are now undervalued, often being mass-produced for products with a short
48 lifespan, resulting in a rapid accumulation of plastic waste. This, coupled with inadequate waste
49 management systems that fail to capture the various plastic wastes and their embedded values, has led
50 to plastic waste becoming a ubiquitous pollutant in our environment.

51 Geyer estimates that between 1950-2017, only 10% of all plastics ever made had been recycled, 14%
52 had been incinerated, and 76% had been discarded into landfills (Geyer, 2020). This issue is more dire
53 in low- to middle-income countries, which tend to have poorer waste management infrastructure,
54 resulting in a higher prevalence of mismanaged waste. Meijer *et al.* estimated that globally, 67.5 trillion
55 metric tonnes (t) of mismanaged plastic waste are produced annually, with 1.5% of this leaking into the
56 ocean (Meijer *et al.*, 2021). It is now acknowledged that plastics make up the majority of waste present
57 in the marine environment (Gregory and Ryan, 1997; Barnes *et al.*, 2009; Galgani, Hanke and Maes,
58 2015).

59 Although only 20% of plastics entering the ocean are thought to originate from marine-based activities,
60 fishing gear accounts for 10% of marine plastic waste and represents the highest proportion of
61 macroplastics floating on the ocean's surface (Thomas, Dorey and Obaidullah, 2019; Morales-Caselles
62 *et al.*, 2021). In some regions, fishing plastic waste (FPW) makes up the majority of litter present.
63 Specifically, it accounted for 100% of litter found in the North and Northeast Faroe-Shetland Channels

64 and >85% of litter found in the Condor Seamount, Hatton Bank and Wyville-Thomson Ridge (Pham *et*
65 *al.*, 2014). Moreover, 52% of the plastics found in the Great Pacific Garbage Patch originate from
66 fishing activities, of which fishing nets formed 86% of the 42kt of megaplastics (>50cm) present
67 (Lebreton *et al.*, 2018; Thomas, Dorey and Obaidullah, 2019). Despite this, current research focuses
68 predominantly on land-based sources of plastics.

69 FPW has been shown to have physical and physiological impacts on marine biota and coastal
70 environments and, consequently, human populations (Jones, 1995; Dau *et al.*, 2009; Macfadyen,
71 Huntington and Cappell, 2009; Link, Segal and Casarini, 2019; Watson *et al.*, 2022). Coastal
72 communities in low-middle-income countries are heavily reliant on marine ecosystems for their
73 livelihoods, including sustenance, trade, tourism, and cultural value (Rao *et al.*, 2016; Robertson and
74 Midway, 2019; Wei, Xu and Wall, 2023) and are vulnerable to changes in the marine environment
75 (Aswani *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, with most the world's capture fisheries being based in these regions,
76 coastal communities here may be at greater risk from the effects of this pollution (Apete, Martin and
77 Iacovidou, 2024). Understanding how FPW impact them is necessary to devise solutions with these
78 communities and for governments to design effective policy interventions.

79 Recent literature that explores the impacts of marine debris on coastal communities largely overlooks
80 FPW (UN, 2016b, p. 8). While reviews have been carried out on the impacts of abandoned fishing gear,
81 none focus specifically on gear made from plastics, despite the consensus that plastics are the dominant
82 material for this equipment (Jones, 1995; Macfadyen, Huntington and Cappell, 2009; Link, Segal and
83 Casarini, 2019; Watson *et al.*, 2022). These reviews typically analyse items such as lines, nets and ropes
84 but omit the impacts of associated equipment, such as polystyrene storage boxes and plastic ice bags
85 used for storage and preservation (Do and Armstrong, 2023). Furthermore, most studies emphasise
86 environmental impacts, with limited attention to the broader impacts on coastal ecosystems, particularly
87 in developing countries. Although existing research has identified negative impacts on provisioning,
88 supporting and cultural services, none addressed regulating services. In addition, there is limited recent
89 literature on the socioeconomic impacts of FPW in coastal communities (Jones, 1995; Macfadyen,
90 Huntington and Cappell, 2009). In many of these communities, there is a heavy reliance on the marine
91 environment for service provision, yet they face increasing pressure from inadequate solid waste
92 management systems (Arifin *et al.*, 2023; Daniel and Thomas, 2023). This underlines the urgent need
93 for addressing both the environmental and socioeconomic dimensions of FPW, particularly in regions
94 with high dependency on marine ecosystems and limited waste infrastructure.

95 The growing prevalence of FPW in the marine environment highlights the crucial need for a systematic
96 approach to understanding its systemic impacts on coastal communities. Systematic evidence maps
97 (SEM) provide an effective method for amassing and assessing the existing evidence base, identifying
98 knowledge gaps, and guiding future research priorities. Such analyses can reveal critical blind spots in

120 [semi-structured interviews](#). By mapping the [available](#) evidence, we will widen and improve our
 121 understanding of the complex interrelationships within these [environmental, technological, political,](#)
 122 [economic and social](#) sub-systems. The findings will enable practitioners to identify knowledge gaps and
 123 potential positive and negative feedback loops, reducing the risk of adopting a siloed approach to
 124 problem-solving, thereby fostering integrated, sustainable solutions.

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126 1.2. Definitions and Disambiguation of Terms

127 1.2.1. Coastal Communities

128 There are many definitions of coastal communities in the literature, specifically referring to human
 129 settlements (**Table 1**). A commonly used definition incorporates a 100-kilometre (km) inland boundary
 130 based on analyses of human population distribution, which revealed a steep population density gradient
 131 over this distance (Small and Nicholls, 2003; Small and Cohen, 2004). However, [for our systematic](#)
 132 [evidence mapping, our focus is not on geographic proximity but rather on populations and communities](#)
 133 [whose livelihoods are directly dependent on coastal and marine resources. As a result, While populations](#)
 134 [and communities beyond further than the 100km threshold, are often bound to inland activities and](#)
 135 [can may not be linked to the coast socio-economically \(e.g., through fishing or cultural identity\), others](#)
 136 [may or depend on coastal systems/infrastructure \(e.g., inland agricultural communities dependent on](#)
 137 [estuaries\). Therefore when investigating impacts on these communities,](#) it is important to consider
 138 [populations and communities their](#) reliance on surrounding natural resources, as emphasised in
 139 definitions by Green 2.0 (2022); the Coastal Communities Alliance (2024), [particularly when](#)
 140 [investigating the socioeconomic, political, and technical impacts](#). These natural resources include the
 141 biotic and abiotic elements of marine and coastal ecosystems, which directly influence the ecosystem
 142 services available to coastal communities.

144 **Table 1: Definitions of coastal communities found in the literature**

Definition	Source
Populations within 100 horizontal km of the coastline and 100 vertical meters of sea level.	(Small and Nicholls, 2003)
Any coastal settlement within a(n English) local authority area whose boundaries include (English) foreshore, including local authorities whose boundaries only include estuarine foreshore. Coastal settlements include seaside towns, ports and other areas which have a clear connection to the coastal economy.	(Coastal Communities Alliance, 2024)
Coastal populations are those living within 100 km of the coast, and excluding countries without territory within 100 km of a	(Barbier, 2015)

coastline measured using an Azimuthal Equidistant (world) projection.

Percentage of total population living within 100 km of the coastline. (UN, 2017; UNEP, 2017)

Residents living within 100 km of the shore. (Maul and Duedall, 2021)

One that lives near the coast and/or utilizes coastal resources and the ocean for its livelihood in a manner shaped by cultural heritage or economic needs. (Green 2.0, 2022) – environmental racial diversity NGO

People living within 100 km from the coast. (Barros *et al.*, 2023)

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146 Further for this study, our understanding of “coastal communities” will be defined as “*individuals or*
147 *groups of individuals living near the coast and/or relying on coastal and ocean resources for their*
148 *livelihoods, in ways influenced by cultural heritage or economic need, and interconnected with the*
149 *ecosystems that support them*”. This definition accounts for both the geographical proximity and the
150 socioeconomic, cultural and ecological interconnections on which the livelihoods and well-being of
151 coastal communities rely.

152 1.2.2. Fishing Plastic Waste

153 Currently, there is no universally accepted definition for “fishing plastic waste”. To address this gap,
154 we developed a definition by analysing existing definitions of fishing plastic equipment, referred to
155 here as “fishing plastics” or “fishing gear”, and reviewing how FPW is characterised in the literature.

156 The definitions of fishing gear (**Table 2**) vary in the specificity of the components included. However,
157 they consistently agree that *fishing gear refers to any equipment or combination of components used*
158 *or capable of being used to capture, control for subsequent capture, or harvest marine or freshwater*
159 *organisms and biological resources*. Most descriptions of fishing gear are derived from the
160 International Standard Statistical Classification of Fishing Gear (ISSCFG) (He *et al.*, 2021), which was
161 designed to support fisheries and marine conservation research. The ISSCFG classifies fishing gear
162 based on physical characteristics, operational methods, and fish capture mechanisms. The major types
163 of fishing gear and their material compositions are summarised in **Table S1** (*Annex 1*).

164

165 **Table 2: Definitions of fishing gear found in the literature**

Definition of Fishing Gear	Source
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A fishing gear is any physical device or part thereof, or combination of items that may be placed on or in the water or on the seabed with the intended purpose of capturing or controlling for subsequent capture or harvesting marine or freshwater organisms.	The International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships (MARPOL), Annex V (MEPC, 2011)
“Fishing gear” means any net or other implement or means used or capable of being used for the harvesting of marine resources.	Namibia’s Marine Resources Act, 27 of 2000 (Republic of Namibia, 2000)
Fishing gear means any equipment, implement or other thing that can be used in the act of fishing, and includes any fishing net, rope, line, float, trap, hook, winch, or associated boat or aircraft.	Fisheries Act No. 10 of 2014, (Republic of Vanuatu, 2014)
“Sea fishing equipment” means (a) fishing nets or any other equipment used during sea fishing (including, for example, equipment used to navigate, or to deter animals that are not intended to be caught), or (b) equipment used to monitor sea fishing.	Fisheries Act 2020, (UK Government, 2020)
“Fishing gear” means any item or piece of equipment that is used in fishing or aquaculture to target, capture or rear marine biological resources or that is floating on the sea surface, and is deployed with the objective of attracting and capturing or of rearing such marine biological resources.	Directive (EU) 2019/904 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment (European Parliament, Council of the European Union, 2019)
Fishing gear includes any net, line, pot, bob, trap, dredge, apparatus, device, or other thing that is used or is capable of being used for the purposes of taking fish.	Fisheries (Amateur Fishing) Regulations 2013 New Zealand (Governor-General, 2013)
Facilities and equipment or other objects that are used for fishing.	Ministerial Regulation 33/PERMEN-KP/2021 – (Minister of Marine Affairs And Fisheries of The Republic of Indonesia, 2021)

166

167 Defining fishing plastic becomes more complicated when looking at how FPW is characterised in the
 168 literature. Fishing plastics also encompass ancillary items used in fishing activities, such as buoys,
 169 gloves, fish storage boxes, strapping bands, plastic bottles carrying stroke oil, and plastic ice bags for
 170 fish preservation that become waste (**Table S2** in *Annex 2*).

171 In the literature, FPW is characterised as materials, components and products that have been abandoned,
 172 lost, or discarded in the environment and are associated with the act of fishing (Claereboudt, 2004;
 173 Edyvane *et al.*, 2004; Moriarty *et al.*, 2016; UNEP, 2016; Consoli *et al.*, 2019; European Commission,
 174 2019; Simeonova and Chaturkova, 2020; GESAMP, 2021; Pinheiro *et al.*, 2021, 2023; ICES, 2022;
 175 Nguyen *et al.*, 2022; Watson *et al.*, 2022). These ancillary items are necessary for the handling, storage,
 176 and preservation of captured or harvested marine organisms but are often made from polymers also
 177 commonly found in marine debris of terrestrial origin (e.g., polystyrene being used for fish storage
 178 boxes, as well as food containers). In some fisheries, particularly small-scale and artisanal activities,

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179 marine resources are brought directly to shore for sale, often using the same plastic materials used
180 during fishing (e.g., fish boxes, gloves) (UN, 2016a, p. 4; Pardie and Campion, 2022; Cunha *et al.*,
181 2023). As this study focuses on the global impacts of FPW on coastal communities, particularly those
182 dependent on small-scale, artisanal fisheries, our definition includes plastics used for storing and
183 preserving the catch during direct sales on shore. Excluding this aspect risks overlooking a critical
184 component, potentially leading to an incomplete understanding of what encompasses FPW and,
185 subsequently, their environmental and socio-economic impacts, leading to partial or ineffective
186 solutions.

187 Considering these definitions and conditions, we developed the following working definition of FPW
188 as “*a piece, part or combination of equipment made from plastic polymers that are used or capable of*
189 *being used to capture, control for subsequent capture, or harvest, marine or freshwater organisms,*
190 *including ancillary plastic items that support these activities or are used for the storage and*
191 *preservation of these organisms until sold or allocated for personal consumption by the fisher, that has*
192 *been abandoned, lost or otherwise discarded in the marine or coastal environment*”. This definition
193 includes only ancillary items explicitly linked to fishing practices (e.g., gloves, storage boxes, ice bags).
194 It includes plastic items used to store gear during fishing activities, as well as repurposed consumer
195 plastics used in fishing activities (e.g., plastic bottles repurposed as bailing containers). This definition
196 but excludes plastics associated with fish farming equipment and aquaculture. This broad definition
197 aims to prevent is intended to ensure that variation the diversity of in how FPW is described in literature
198 from being a barrier to does not hinder the extraction of relevant data.

199

200 1.2.3. Multidimensional impacts

201 This SEM will explore five key dimensions of impact: (i) environmental; (ii) social; (iii) economic; (iv)
202 technical; and (v) political impacts. These dimensions align with the five interacting sub-systems of the
203 ‘five levels of information’, or ‘5LoI’ framework of the Complex Value Optimisation for Resource
204 Recovery (CVORR) systems-based tool (Iacovidou *et al.*, 2020; **Figure 2**).

205 This facilitates a holistic understanding of the complex interrelationships within these systems.

206

207

208 **Figure 2: The ‘5LoI’ (five levels of information), a conceptual framework that enables the**
 209 **understanding of the dynamics, drivers and barriers of resource recovery systems; Source:**
 210 **(Iacovidou *et al.*, 2020).**

211

212 Environmental impacts fall within the 1st level of information, the ‘Natural environment and
 213 provisioning services’. The SEM will explore the impacts of FPW on ecosystem health (i.e., marine
 214 organisms and their habitats), biodiversity and ecosystem services that coastal communities depend on
 215 for their well-being (via ecosystem services).

216 Technical impacts fall within the 2nd level of information, ‘Technologies, infrastructure and innovation
 217 level’. Technical impacts relate to a "technique", i.e., a specialised method or procedure, and challenges
 218 related to fishing gear functionality, fishing activities or operations and waste management systems.
 219 Therefore, technical effects to coastal communities once plastic fishing gear becomes waste/they are
 220 exposed to FPW in the environment include changes in the way communities conduct fishing activities
 221 (e.g., reduced functionality of gear, altered fishing techniques) or methods of dealing with this waste at
 222 end-of-use/end-of-life (e.g., repair, repurposing, recycling, collection for disposal, energy recovery).
 223 This may also relate to what indigenous knowledge and technical skills may have been lost at the end
 224 of the use/life stage due to replacing traditional fishing gear with plastic fishing gear.

225 Political impacts support the 3rd level of information: ‘Governance, regulatory framework and political
 226 landscape’. This refers to policy responses from the government in coastal regions to address FPW.
 227 Ultimately, any policy proposed in response to FPW will have consequences for the region’s inhabitants.

228 Economic impacts support the 4th level of information, ‘Activities performed by businesses and the
 229 market’. The SEM will include the impacts of FPW on livelihoods, including financial implications
 230 from the presence of FPW on individuals and the broader coastal communities.

231 Social impacts support the 5th level of information, ‘Patterns of behaviour related to meeting human and
 232 societal needs’. The SEM will focus on the impacts of FPW on human well-being and community
 233 dynamics, including cultural aspects and perspectives on FPW.

234 1.3. Objectives

235 Well-formulated research statements are critical for ensuring the accuracy and coherence of other
 236 review components, including the literature search strategy, data extraction, synthesis, and presentation
 237 of findings. The PEO (Population, Exposure, Outcome) framework (Moola *et al.*, 2015) is a widely
 238 used tool for exploring associations between specific exposures and outcomes, particularly in
 239 qualitative research.

240 **Our research question is articulated as follows:** What are the environmental, social, technical,
 241 economic and political impacts of FPW-associated pollution on coastal communities?

242 Using the PEO framework (Table 3), the specific objectives of this SEM are to:

- 243 1. Identify, group and organise existing primary evidence on the multidimensional
 244 (environmental, social, economic, political, technical) impacts (outcomes) of FPW (exposure)
 245 on coastal communities, inclusive of the ecosystems these communities rely on (population).
- 246 2. Present the evidence in a user-friendly format, including an interactive online cause-effect
 247 diagram and dashboard that will be made publicly accessible to facilitate knowledge sharing.
- 248 3. Identify knowledge gaps and evidence clusters across taxa (population), FPW types (exposure),
 249 and multidimensional effects (outcomes) to inform future research needs and/or analysis.

251 **Table 3: PEO framework developed for this protocol - Population, Exposure, Outcome**

Element of PEO framework	Description of the PEO element developed for this protocol
Population	Individuals or groups of individuals living near the coast and/or relying on coastal and ocean resources for their livelihoods, in ways influenced by cultural heritage or economic need, and interconnected with the ecosystems that support them.
Exposure	A piece, part or combination of equipment made from plastic polymers that are used or capable of being used to capture, control for subsequent capture, or harvest, marine or freshwater organisms, including ancillary plastic items that support these activities or are used for the storage and preservation of these organisms until sold or allocated for personal

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Outcomes

consumption by the fisher, that has been abandoned, lost or otherwise discarded in the marine or coastal environment.

Environmental impacts caused by the presence and exposure of human and non-human populations or communities to FPW in the marine and coastal environments. This includes physical harm to marine life (e.g., entanglement and ingestion, habitat damage), toxicological impacts (e.g., chemicals leaching, microplastics), disruption of ecosystem services (e.g., impact on marine food web and flora), contribution to climatic change (e.g., greenhouse gases emissions).

Social impacts of the presence or interaction of FPW with human and non-human populations or communities in the marine and coastal environments. This includes impacts on health and well-being or coastal communities.

Technical impacts arising from the presence or interaction of FPW in the marine and coastal environments. These include technical challenge such as damage to fishing equipment (e.g., gear entanglement, gear loss and equipment degradation due to wear and tear), repair and recycling.

Economic impacts to individuals, groups of individuals or economies caused by the presence or interaction of FPW in the marine and coastal environments. These include impacts on livelihoods, fisheries, tourism, and economic activities dependent on healthy marine and coastal ecosystems.

Political impacts resulting from the presence of FPW in the marine and coastal environments, particularly on local policy and governance. This may include the influence on local government activities, regulations and initiatives aimed at managing the impacts of FPW on ecosystems or managing and reducing FPW.

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252 2. Methods

253 This protocol was drafted following the updated 2015 PRISMA-P guidelines (Preferred Reporting Items
254 for Systematic review and Meta-Analysis Protocols; *Annex 3*) (Moher *et al.*, 2015; Page *et al.*, 2021)
255 and giving due consideration to the recommendations for the Conduct of Systematic Reviews in
256 Toxicology and Environmental Health Research (COSTER) (Whaley *et al.*, 2020).

257 2.1. Information sources

258 Peer-reviewed academic literature will be found by searching on Web of Science (WoS), Scopus and
259 Pubmed electronic indexes, as well as Business Source Complete, CINAHL Plus, EconLit, GreenFile,
260 and Humanities International Index via the EBSCOHost Platform. All databases will be accessed using
261 the University College London subscription (as of December 2024). Pilot searches demonstrated that
262 this combination of databases provides adequate coverage for the diverse range of outcomes to be
263 explored. Details of each database's disciplinary coverage can be found in the supplementary material
264 (*Annex 4*). The searches will be complemented by [reference mining](#) [direct citation searching \(i.e.,](#)
265 [snowballing\)](#), [conducted using the TARCiS checklist developed by Hirst and colleagues](#) (Hirst *et al.*,

266 2024). Springer was considered; however, it yielded an unmanageable number of results (>500,000).
267 Conversely, Anthropology Plus, SocIndex, and Child Development and Adolescent Studies via the
268 EBSCOHost Platform, and JSTOR were also considered, but all yielded an insufficient number of
269 relevant results (<3%).

270 All indexes will be searched using title, abstract and keyword fields. This will be achieved on WoS by
271 searching by Topic in the core collection and all databases subscribed to by University College London
272 (as of December 2024). If a search update is required, the search will be repeated, however, limited to
273 studies published since the date of the last search.

274 Grey literature searches will be manually conducted on repositories of The World Bank Group, the
275 United Nations (UN), the Organization for Economic Co-Operation and Development (OECD), as well
276 as Non-Governmental Organization (NGO) reports and published research available via the Google
277 search engine.

278 Literature ~~and all systematic review processes will be~~ screening will be managed and coordinated with
279 the support of the freely available online tool CADIMA, established in a close collaboration between
280 the Julius Kühn-Institut and the Collaboration for Environmental Evidence (Kohl *et al.*, 2018). The
281 reference manager, Citavi (Swiss Academic Software, 2023), will be used to support the retrieval of full
282 texts of studies. Data will be collected and presented using Microsoft Excel.

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283 2.2. Search Strategy

284 We developed search strings for each database to reflect our PEO framework in collaboration with a
285 librarian specialist (JMP). Population terms were developed relating to aspects of the study subject (i.e.,
286 community, coastal, environment, organism) and species group (i.e., human, animal, plant, bacteria,
287 fungi). As plastic is the standard material used in fishing gear, it is common for titles and abstracts not
288 to reference plastic materials in papers related to the effects of fishing plastic waste. Titles and abstracts
289 either describe the effects of 1) specific items of gear, with no explicit mention of fishing or material,
290 2) “fishing-related” pollution, or 3) marine debris, with no mention of fishing or material. Therefore, it
291 was important for exposure terms to sufficiently capture this variation by including general terms for
292 fishing plastics (e.g., fishing gear, fishing nets, rope), terms related to the source of the item (e.g., fisher*
293 related, originating from fishing, derived from fishing), the material (e.g., fishing *plastic, plastic
294 polymer names), and waste terms (e.g., pollut*, derelict). Proximity operators (e.g., fisher* NEAR
295 origin) were employed here to capture these items.

296 Pilot searches revealed a need to group microplastic terms with waste terms, as due to these intrinsically
297 being waste abstracts, they did not tend to use waste terms (e.g., litter, pollution) to describe them. To
298 capture relevant literature where fishing plastic waste is described as marine debris in the abstract, we
299 also searched for fishing-related terms in the keywords field. No search limitation (i.e., NOT terms)

300 were used to prevent excluding studies reporting on more than one population/exposure/outcome. The
301 search was not restricted by language; however, as the search was conducted in English, a title and
302 abstract in English were required to assess the relevance of the study.

303 A comprehensive list of outcome terms was devised related to health effects (e.g., inflammation,
304 oxidative stress, genotoxicity, apoptosis, necrosis), ecologically relevant effects (e.g., survival,
305 reproduction, growth, development, behaviour, invasive species, greenhouse gas emissions), social
306 effects (e.g., culture, recreation, education), economic effects (e.g., econom*, livelihood, income),
307 political (e.g., govern*, poli*, legislation), and technical effects (e.g., technique, dispose, reuse,
308 repurpose). Terms related to known methods of estimating these outcomes were also used (e.g., LCA,
309 cost*benefit). Outcome terms were included as they effectively refined the results without
310 compromising a significant number of relevant papers (2% relevant papers missed). Terms were
311 searched for individually on each database to confirm their relevance, then combined with Boolean and
312 proximity operators to devise a sufficiently sensitive whilst selective strategy (*Table S4 in Annex 5*).

313 Details of the performance-piloted search terms and strings and the agreed final search strings can be
314 found in *Annex 6*. As it is not possible for any search string to capture all existing literature or to be
315 completely free of bias, we undertook a validation exercise using a subset of articles (n=303) identified
316 as relevant to the objectives of this study (*Annex 7*). These articles were ~~identified~~ selected during the
317 initial scoping search using expert knowledge or due to their inclusion in prior articles reviewing the
318 evidence of environmental, economic, social, and/or technical/technological effects of marine plastic
319 pollution (Browne et al., 2015; Li, Tse and Fok, 2016; Stelfox, Hudgins and Sweet, 2016; Agamuthu et
320 al., 2019; Angiolillo and Fortibuoni, 2020; Kumar et al., 2021; Costa et al., 2022; Hernandez et al.,
321 2022; Watson et al., 2022; Agarwala, 2023; Gilman et al., 2023; Nama et al., 2023; Kibria, 2024). They
322 include papers related to each outcome category and contain varying levels of detail in the title/abstract
323 describing the type of ~~the~~ fishing plastic waste. Comparing the list of relevant articles to articles
324 retrieved using our search string on WoS, we achieved a retrieval rate of 878%. This increased to 934%
325 when searching in Scopus, PubMed or EBSCOHost for missed articles. Thus, we are confident that our
326 search strategy is robust enough to identify the body of evidence relevant to our research aims.

327 Grey literature search strings will be adapted to fit the functionalities and filters available for retrieving
328 results from these sources.

329 **2.3. Eligibility Criteria**

330 The PEO statement (Table 4) informed the development of clear inclusion and exclusion criteria to
331 ensure transparent and reproducible study eligibility screening. These criteria enable a systematic
332 approach to study selection for the SEM.

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333 This SEM is focused on evidence of real-world impacts ~~to~~on coastal communities and the natural
 334 environment they depend on. Thus, laboratory, in vitro, and ~~in~~-silico studies were excluded, as they
 335 typically rely on controlled conditions, technical proxies, or sample types that may not reflect the
 336 complex, real-world socio-technical, and environmental contexts relevant to this evidence mapping.
 337 Including such studies could introduce context-specific biases and limit the generalisability of findings
 338 to field-based, observational settings.

339

340 **Table 4:** Eligibility criteria for inclusion and exclusion of the PEO framework.

<u>PEO element</u>	<u>Inclusion criteria</u>	<u>Exclusion criteria</u>
<u>Population</u>	<p>All the following must be true:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Any defined individual, group or assemblage of individuals or species</u> • <u>human or non-human (Vertebrates including humans, Invertebrates, Micro-organisms)</u> • <u>Relying on coastal and ocean resources</u> 	<p>If any of these is true, the study is excluded:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Undefined group(s) e.g. global, nationals or regional population</u>
<u>Exposure</u>	<p>All the following must be true:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Fragments of any size of plastic polymers (macro-, micro-, or nano-)</u> • <u>Polymer types: ...</u> • <u>Waste (no longer in active use)</u> • <u>Origin attributed to previous use as fishing gear</u> • <u>Repurposed consumer plastics used in fishing activities</u> • <u>Plastic items used to store gear during fishing activities</u> 	<p>If any of these is true, the study is excluded:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Biodegradable plastic or natural polymers</u> • <u>Still in active use</u> • <u>Waste of unspecified origin</u> • <u>Waste from activities other than fishing</u> • <u>Waste from fish farms and aquaculture</u> • <u>Waste or fragments from boats and ships regardless of whether they are used in fishing or other activities.</u>
<u>Outcomes</u>	<p>Any of the following is true for:</p> <p><u>Environmental impacts.</u></p> <p><u>Field, in situ or observational study measuring any of the following.</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>physical harm to marine life caused by macroplastic (e.g., entanglement and ingestion, ghost fishing, smothering and habitat damage). These do not need to describe a population-</u> 	<p>If any of these is true, the study is excluded:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Conducted under controlled laboratory conditions</u> • <u>In vitro or in silico experiments</u>

- level impact to be accepted, as plastics of this size have inherent physiological effects (i.e., gastrointestinal tract function, motility, or presence of a foreign object attached to the body).
- impacts to marine biotic and abiotic elements.
 - disruption of ecosystem services

If these are the only outcomes measured, the study is excluded:

- Abundance of any type of plastic
- Ingestion or inhalation on NMPs
- Characteristics of nano- or microplastics ingested or inhaled by an organism

OR Social impacts, objectively measured or perceived related to.

- Health and well-being
- Human rights,
- Safety,
- Justice,
- Culture and recreation,
- Education,
- Access to services
- Working life (e.g. labour rights, working conditions)

If these are the only outcomes, the study is excluded:

- estimate(s) of future impacts
- theoretical studies

OR Economic impacts, objectively measured or perceived on.

- Livelihoods,
- Trade
- Any financial costs/benefits

If these are the only outcomes, the study is excluded:

- estimate(s) of future impacts
- theoretical studies

OR Political impacts, including.

- Local or regional responses (e.g., initiatives/schemes, action plans, policies, legislation)
- Responses at the interface of local and national policy that provide empirical insights from cross-scale governance dynamics/structures from local, national and global scale.
- Enforcement of new or existing responses

If these are the only outcomes measured, the study is excluded:

- Exclusively national and multilateral governmental responses
- Outcomes of governmental responses on FPW based on stakeholder perceptions

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OR Technical impacts, including.

- Local techniques employed for fishing gear or active fishing
 - Local management at the end-of-use/end-of-life stage
- If these are the only outcomes measured, the study is excluded:
- Global, international, corporate or national techniques
 - Technological solutions

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2.3.1. Refinement via Piloting of the Screening Process

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A first consistency check was conducted to develop and refine the eligibility criteria. All search results were imported into Cadima, where duplicate records were removed, leaving a total of 9,581 unique references. Three reviewers piloted the Title and Abstract screening by applying the initial eligibility criteria to the titles and abstracts of 7.83% (n=750) of the results, as this is the maximum allowed on Cadima. This resulted in 121 papers being progressed to full text screening; therefore, we estimated ~1400 papers may still be progressed for full text screening. This high number of eligible studies would be challenging to extract data from within the resources allocated to this project. It is common for literature exploring the impacts of marine plastics (especially microplastics and smaller) not to include the source of the plastic in the abstract. A permissive interpretation of the eligibility criteria would further introduce uncertainty and weaken our analysis of the evidence. To limit this, we sought to refine our eligibility criteria to reduce the 89 of 121 eligible rated unclear at the Title and Abstract screening stage.

~~The PEO statement informed the development of clear inclusion and exclusion criteria to ensure transparent and reproducible study eligibility screening. These criteria enable a systematic approach to study selection for the SEM.~~

~~A first consistency check was conducted to develop and refine the eligibility criteria. All search results were imported into Cadima where duplicate records were removed, leaving a total of 9,581 unique references. Three reviewers performed a piloted the Title and Abstract screening by applying the initial eligibility criteria to the title and abstracts of 7.83% (n=750) of the results, as this is the maximum allowed on Cadima. This resulted in 121 papers being progressed to full text screening, therefore we estimated ~1400 papers may still be progressed for full text screening. This high number of eligible studies would be challenging to extract data from within the resources allocated to this project. It is common for literature exploring the impacts of marine plastics (especially microplastics and smaller) not to include the source of the plastic in the abstract. A permissive interpretation of the eligibility criteria would further introduce uncertainty and weaken our analysis of the evidence. To limit this, we sought to refine our eligibility criteria to reduce the 89 of 121 eligible rated unclear at Title and Abstract screening stage.~~

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370 The reviewers noted a high occurrence of microplastic papers that did not explicitly refer to FPW in the
 371 title or abstract, so needed to be progressed to full text screening to determine their relevance. To reduce
 372 this, microplastic papers will only progress to full text screening if they relate to direct impacts to marine
 373 biotic (i.e., impacts following ingestion/inhalation) and abiotic elements. In addition, many studies were
 374 identified that made inferences about potential impacts in the abstract after solely characterising or
 375 estimating the abundance of fishing plastic waste in the environment. It was decided that only studies
 376 that directly investigate impacts would be accepted.

377 Furthermore, studies on political impacts will only be progressed that impact on our defined 'coastal
 378 communities' population (i.e., at the local level). Studies at the interface of local and national policy
 379 will be included if they provide empirical insights from cross-scale governance dynamics/structures
 380 from local, national and global scales. ~~Whilst those exclusively~~ at the national and multilateral levels
 381 will be excluded. Studies reporting on the outcomes of governmental responses on FPW (e.g.,
 382 government clean-up project), based on stakeholder perceptions will also be excluded.

383 Finally, only studies on technical impacts to fishing technique and management of FPW at end-of-
 384 use/end-of-life will be progressed. Studies on technological impacts will be excluded.

385 A second consistency check was conducted applying the new eligibility criteria to the 121 progressed
 386 studies using Microsoft Excel (*Annex 8*). This process reduced the number of progressed studies to 55.
 387 Further refinement of the search strings to reduce ambiguous studies produced 6,237 results. Applying
 388 the outcome of the consistency check (depicted in *Annex 9*) we estimate ~400 papers may still be
 389 progressed to full text screening. The logic underlying the application of the eligibility criteria is
 390 detailed in **Table 4**.

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392 **Table 4:** Eligibility criteria for inclusion and exclusion of the PEO framework.

PEO element	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Population	<p>All the following must be true:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Any defined individual, group or assemblage of individuals or species human or non-human (Vertebrates including humans, Invertebrates, Micro-organisms) Relying on coastal and ocean resources 	<p>If any of these is true, the study is excluded:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Undefined group(s) e.g. global, national or regional population
Exposure	<p>All the following must be true:</p>	<p>If any of these is true, the study is excluded:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fragments of any size of plastic polymers (macro-, micro-, or nano-) • Polymer types: ... • Waste (no longer in active use) • Origin attributed to previous use as fishing gear 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodegradable plastic or natural polymers • Still in active use • waste of unspecified origin • Waste from activities other than fishing • Waste from fish farms and aquaculture • Waste or fragments from boats and ships regardless of whether they are used in fishing or other activities.
<p>Outcomes</p>	<p>Any of the following is true for:</p> <p>Environmental impacts, Field, in situ or observational study measuring any of the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • physical harm to marine life caused by macroplastic (e.g., entanglement and ingestion, ghost fishing, smothering and habitat damage). These do not need to describe a population-level impact to be accepted, as plastics of this size have inherent physiological effects (i.e., gastrointestinal tract function, motility, or presence of a foreign object attached to the body). • impacts to marine biotic and abiotic elements. • disruption of ecosystem services <p>OR Social impacts, objectively measured or perceived related to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health and well-being • Human rights, • Safety, • Justice, • Culture and recreation, • Education, • Access to services • Working life (e.g. labour rights, working conditions) 	<p>If any of these is true, the study is excluded:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conducted under controlled laboratory conditions • In vitro or in silico experiments <p>If these are the only outcomes measured, the study is excluded:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Abundance of any type of plastic • Ingestion or inhalation on NMPs • Characteristics of nano or microplastics ingested or inhaled by an organism <p>If these are the only outcomes, the study is excluded:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • estimate(s) of future impacts • theoretical studies

<p>OR Economic impacts, objectively measured or perceived on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Livelihoods, • Trade • Any financial costs/benefits 	<p>If these are the only outcomes, the study is excluded:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • estimate(s) of future impacts • theoretical studies
<p>OR Political impacts, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local or regional responses (e.g., initiatives/schemes, action plans, policies, legislation) • Enforcement of new or existing responses 	<p>If these are the only outcomes measured, the study is excluded:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • national and multilateral governmental responses
<p>OR Technical impacts, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local techniques employed for fishing gear or active fishing • Local management at the end-of-use/end of life stage 	<p>If these are the only outcomes measured, the study is excluded:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global, international, corporate or national techniques • Technological solutions

393 **2.4. Study selection**

394 Title-abstract and full-text screening will be conducted by LA in Cadima. Title-abstract screening will
395 be set up with a 10% overlap (i.e., LA will screen 100% of the studies and 10% of the studies will be
396 screened in duplicate by OM and EI) as a quality control step. The full text of studies included after
397 title-abstract screening will be retrieved and screened in Cadima - again with a 10% overlap as a quality
398 control check while one screener (LA) conducts most of the screening. Discrepancies between
399 reviewers will be resolved through discussion between reviewers as soon as they arise to allow for the
400 rectification of any systematic error or drift in the interpretation of eligibility criteria to be addressed as
401 soon as detected. An unexplained high rate of discrepancies (> 5%, checked weekly) may trigger a
402 second round of screening as a corrective step. We will report the recorded discrepancy rates. The
403 reasons for the exclusion of studies after the assessment of the full text will be recorded.
404 Multiple reports of the same study (e.g. multiple publications, conference abstracts, etc.) will not be
405 excluded, but instead, the methodological information from each of the reports will be collated as part
406 of the data recording process as one unit of evidence.

407

2.5. Data extraction and data items

A data extraction template in Microsoft Excel was developed, piloted and revised following the piloting exercise. Three reviewers individually extracted data from a sample of papers (n=3) identified as relevant during the second consistency check. The results of these individual data extraction exercises were compared to ensure parity (*Annex 10*). This piloting exercise generated important discussions about what one unit of evidence should consist of and avoid the multiplication of rows ~~to capture all individual reported effects in detail~~. ~~Following piloting, it was agreed that capturing high levels of detailed information under each outcome was neither necessary nor of feasible to meet the aims of this systematic evidence map for this study. As such, it was~~ We decided ~~to that we would capture broad categories and allow the selection multiple entries rather than triggering a separate entry (new row)~~. Google Forms was tested to achieve this and rejected. We found using a Visual Basic for Applications (VBA) code in Excel (*Annex 11*) to allow the selection of multiple items in drop down lists to be most appropriate for the subsequent production of Tableau visualisations and dashboards. ~~As a result, the authors first investigated the use of a Google form to facilitate the capture of multiple options in drop down menus.~~ Full guidance on the cells in which multiple entries are permitted can be found in the "Instructions" sheet of the Data Extraction Template (*Annex 10*). One reviewer (LA) will extract data from the included records, and 1 in 10 will be extracted in duplicate ~~in parallel~~ by OVM or EI as a quality control step. ~~The error rate will be checked weekly, with a focus on entries which have a material impact on further analyses of the database, specifically consistent categorisation and completeness of extraction. Here, estimating an error rate is more complex and will require qualitative judgement on when an error rate should trigger duplicate extraction of data from studies not included in the quality control check. We will report error rates, differentiating between incompleteness and miscategorisation errors for relevant columns. Google Forms will automatically generate an original record of all extracted data on Google Sheets, which can be reverted to and checked if any errors are made following extraction. Data from this sheet will be copied into a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet, where it will be prepared before Tableau visualisations and dashboards.~~

Commented [OM2]: Please review in line with the work we did developing guidance related to which column we capture multiple entries in and which columns multiple answers trigger a new row, consist of a new unit of evidence.

Commented [OM3R2]: This whole section needs to be amended to reflect the fact that we reverted to Excel.

2.6. Summary measures and synthesis of results

Results will be summarised narratively, and the characteristics and volume of evidence visualised in interactive Tableau ([Salesforce, Inc., 2025](#)) dashboards, allowing quick access to the title and abstract and link to included studies. Analyses may include publication and trends, geographical distribution of studies per type of FPW or outcome and analyses of categories of effects under each type of impact. ~~As piloting is still in process, this may be revised. This may include, where appropriate, reporting quantitative measures related to the volume or proportion of the body of literature addressing specific aspects (e.g. specific items, or outcomes) but quantitative synthesis of measure of effects are not envisaged.~~ Dummy Tableau visualisations were generated from the results of the data extraction

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443 [piloting exercise. These illustrate how Tableau can help visualise large amounts of data collected in a](https://public.tableau.com/views/ADLFGSEMdummy/DashboardMap2?:language=en-GB&:sid=&:redirect=auth&:display_count=n&:origin=viz_share_link)
444 [database and how interactivity can support reuse and access to the collated references. This can be](https://public.tableau.com/views/ADLFGSEMdummy/DashboardMap2?:language=en-GB&:sid=&:redirect=auth&:display_count=n&:origin=viz_share_link)
445 [accessed here: https://public.tableau.com/views/ADLFGSEMdummy/DashboardMap2?:language=en-](https://public.tableau.com/views/ADLFGSEMdummy/DashboardMap2?:language=en-GB&:sid=&:redirect=auth&:display_count=n&:origin=viz_share_link)
446 [GB&:sid=&:redirect=auth&:display_count=n&:origin=viz_share_link.](https://public.tableau.com/views/ADLFGSEMdummy/DashboardMap2?:language=en-GB&:sid=&:redirect=auth&:display_count=n&:origin=viz_share_link)

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448 2.7. Data Sharing

449 ~~In addition to~~The interactive Tableau dashboards [will be hosted on Tableau Public a free online](#)
450 [platform to share interactive visualisations of public data. The underpinning database ~~to visualise,~~](#)
451 [search and filter the resulting database, this](#) will also be ~~made public~~publicly available as
452 [supplementary material to an open access peer-reviewed scientific articles](#)~~hed~~ as an Excel file.

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454 2.8. Reporting

455 A comprehensive written report, formatted as a peer-reviewed scientific article, will be developed to
456 accompany the systematic map visualizations. This report will ensure the study's results and database
457 are publicly accessible, downloadable, and easily searchable. It will document all phases of the
458 systematic mapping process, including the background and rationale for the study, details and
459 justifications for any deviations from the outlined methods, a summary of the evidence base's volume
460 and characteristics, and recommendations for future primary research to address identified knowledge
461 gaps. Additionally, the report will outline priorities and opportunities for future systematic reviews.
462 Significant priority will be given to adhering to established reporting standards for systematic maps,
463 such as the Reporting Standards for Systematic Evidence Syntheses (ROSES) guidelines (Haddaway et
464 al., 2018).

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467 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

468 **Larisha Apete:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Validation,
469 Writing - original draft, and Writing - review & editing; **Joanne McPhie:** Methodology and Resources;
470 **Eleni Iacovidou:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Funding acquisition, Project administration,
471 Supervision, Validation, and Writing - review & editing; **Olwenn V. Martin:** Conceptualization, Data
472 curation, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Project administration, Software, Supervision, Validation,
473 and Writing - review & editing.

474

475 **Funding source**

476 This work was supported by the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) Doctoral Training
477 Partnership grant (NE/S007229/1).

478

479 **DOI**

480 The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships, which may be considered
481 as potential competing interests: Larisha Apete reports financial support was provided by the Natural
482 Environment Research Council (NERC). Olwenn V. Martin reports a relationship with Food Packaging
483 Forum that includes [scientific advisory](#) board membership, consulting or advisory, and travel
484 reimbursement. Olwenn V. Martin is one of the European Parliament's representatives on the
485 management board of the European Chemical Agency. She is also a member of the OECD's Plastics
486 Expert Group, ~~and sits on the Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) of the Food Packaging Forum.~~ If there
487 are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
488 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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